

Sulphaguanidine Complexes with Bivalent Metals

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Manuscript received 25 October 1975; accepted 11 February 1976

The complexes of Sulphaguanidine with copper, zinc and cadmium when studied by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation showed 1 : 1 complexation. Their stability constants and free energy of formation have been evaluated by employing Job's method of equimolar and non-equimolar solution using optical density and conductance as index property and also potentiometrically using Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique.

SULPHONAMIDES are the drugs of established therapeutic value. Some of the sulphonamides have been used as complexing agent for various metals¹⁻³ and it has been shown by bacteriostatic studies that these complexes are more potent than the parent drug⁴⁻⁵. The present work deals with complexes of sulphaguanidine with copper, cadmium and zinc.

Experimental

All chemicals employed were of Analar grade.

Conductometric measurements were carried out using conductivity bridge (W.T.W. German) and dip type conductivity cell.

Optical density (O.D.) was measured on Beckmann (DU Model) spectrophotometer. pH measurements were carried with a Beckmann pH meter model (H₂) with glass calomel electrode.

Results and Discussion

Conductivity measurements were carried out with 10 ml. 0.2M Sulphaguanidine dissolved and diluted to 100 ml. and titrated with 0.2M salt solutions. The results after applying volume correction were plotted which indicate 2 : 1 complexation.

Job's method of continuous variation⁶ was also applied to determine the ligand metal ratio using $2 \times 10^{-2}M$ solutions of sulphaguanidine and metal salt solution and conductivity as index property.

The stability constants were calculated by extrapolation of Job curves as suggested by Raghav Rao⁷ using the expression :

$$K_{\alpha} = \frac{\alpha^2 C}{(1-\alpha)}$$

where α is the degree of dissociation.

The results are recorded in Table 1.

Job's method of continuous variation (as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁸) using non-equimolar

TABLE 1. STABILITY CONSTANTS AT TEMP. 30°.

S.No.	Complex	Log K	ΔF Kcals/mole
1.	Cu-Sulphaguanidine	4.32	-6.05
2.	Zn-Sulphaguanidine	3.80	-5.30
3.	Cd-Sulphaguanidine	2.75	-3.81

solutions of metal and sulphaguanidine was also applied to determine the stability constants and free energy of formation.

The results are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

S.No.	Complex	log K		ΔF Kcals/mole	
		Conduc- tance	O.D.	Conduc- tance	O.D.
1.	Cu-Sulphaguanidine	4.50	4.45	6.39	6.13
2.	Zn- ,,	3.82	3.80	5.30	5.20
3.	Cd- ,,	2.80	2.81	3.87	3.90

Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{9,10} has been applied to determine the formation constants of the complexes. The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration against sodium hydroxide (CO₂ free)¹¹ of two mixtures :

Mixture 1 : 10 ml. 0.02M Sulphaguanidine
+10 ml. 0.02M per chloric acid.

Mixture 2 : 10 ml. 0.02M Sulphaguanidine.
+10 ml. 0.02M per chloric acid.
+10 ml. 0.02M Metal ion.

such that the concentration of the common ingredients were identical in all cases. Neutral sodium perchlorate was added so as to maintain ionic strength

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($\mu = 0.1M$). The pH measurements were made in a cell similar to that described earlier¹².

$\bar{n}$ values were obtained from Set 1 and Set 2 titration curves. The metal ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal ligand formation curve drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pL_2 values.

The values of stability constant at an ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1M$) are summarised in Table 3.

TABLE 3

S.No.	Complex	log K	$-\Delta F$ Kcals/mole
1.	Cu-Sulphaguanidine	4.01	5.60
2.	Zn-Sulphaguanidine	3.50	4.85
3.	Cd-Sulphaguanidine	2.71	3.80

The results revealed that Cu, Zn and Cd form 1 : 1 complexes and sequence of stability is found to be $Cu > Zn > Cd$ which is in accordance with Irving and Williams^{13,14}.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank CSIR, New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (P.J.).

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